

Denitrification in Sunlight and its Retardation. Part III.

By N. R. DHAR AND S. K. MUKERJI.

In previous publications it has been shown that the loss of nitrogen in the gaseous state takes place in the soil when nitrogenous compounds undergo nitrification in the soil. When the amounts of nitrogenous compounds present or added to the soil are large and the conditions are favourable for their rapid nitrification, there is marked loss of nitrogen in the gaseous state. This type of nitrogen loss, which occurs when the conditions are favourable for oxidation and nitrification of the nitrogenous compounds, was systematically studied by Lipman and Blair (*Soil Sci.*, 1921, 12, 1) and emphasised by Russell ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth," 1932, pp. 367-369) has been satisfactorily explained by Dhar and Mukerji (*Nature*, 1934, 134, 572; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 67, 756). This denitrification is very prominent in tropical countries where due to the high temperature and sunlight, the nitrification is greatly facilitated.

In several publications we have shown that the nitrification of ammonium salts is greatly accelerated by sunlight. In the present communication, the influence of sunlight on the velocity of nitrification of ammonium sulphate and the nitrogen loss consequent on nitrification have been studied, under field conditions, by applying known amounts of ammonium sulphate to plots of lands in the University compound. In order to exclude light, plots of lands to which ammonium sulphate was added, were completely covered with wooden planks. The covered and the uncovered plots were dug up once in ten days for improving their aeration and the conditions of the plot were identical except the ones covered did not receive sunshine. The ammonium sulphate, which was used in these experiments, was dissolved in water and spread over the experimental plots, as uniformly as possible. From time to time soil samples were taken out and the ammoniacal, nitric total nitrogen and carbon were estimated. The following are the experimental results :—

TABLE Ia.

1080 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 36 sq. ft., *i.e.*, 138.6 kg. of N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per acre of land used.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$.	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Uncovered	0.032%	0.0028%	0.0348%	0.14%	0.476%	18th Jan., 1936
Covered	0.0373	0.004	0.0413	0.148	0.48	"
Uncovered	0.008	0.00934	0.01734	0.1081	0.481	30th Jan., 1936
Covered	0.032	0.0056	0.0376	0.1382	0.481	"
Uncovered	0.00582	0.01132	0.0174	0.1032	0.478	19th Feb., 1936
Covered	0.0224	0.0082	0.0306	0.1328	0.478	"
Uncovered	0.00504	0.01194	0.01698	0.0995	0.478	9th Mar., 1936
Covered	0.02176	0.0092	0.031	0.1324	0.472	"
Uncovered	0.00416	0.01224	0.0164	0.0982	0.478	4th Apr., 1936
Covered	0.0211	0.00976	0.0308	0.1312	0.478	"
Uncovered	0.00324	0.01302	0.01636	0.0921	0.478	25th Apr., 1936
Covered	0.0185	0.01144	0.0299	0.1308	0.478	"

TABLE Ib.

2160 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 36 sq. ft., *i.e.*, 277.2 kg. of N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}(\text{O})_4$ per acre of land used.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$.	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Uncovered	0.0468%	0.0028%	0.0496%	0.200%	0.476%	18th Jan., 1936
Covered	0.0624	0.004	0.06664	0.2	0.482	"
Uncovered	0.0234	0.01168	0.03808	0.167	0.481	30th Jan., 1936
Covered	0.05	0.0018	0.0548	0.1902	0.482	"
Uncovered	0.02	0.0148	0.0348	0.1425	0.478	19th Feb., 1936
Covered	0.0442	0.00844	0.0526	0.1842	0.478	"
Uncovered	0.01844	0.01544	0.03388	0.1325	0.478	9th Mar., 1936
Covered	0.0425	0.00936	0.0518	0.1841	0.478	"
Uncovered	0.01784	0.0157	0.03354	0.1281	0.472	4th Apr., 1936
Covered	0.04024	0.01036	0.0508	0.1834	0.478	"
Uncovered	0.00862	0.01848	0.0271	0.1122	0.472	25th Apr., 1936
Covered	0.03824	0.01242	0.0506	0.1832	0.472	"

These experimental results show definitely that the nitrification of ammonium sulphate is much quicker in the plots receiving sunshine than in those which are covered with wooden planks. Moreover, in the uncovered plots there is more nitrogen loss than in the covered plots. Thus when 131.6 kg. of nitrogen were added to the soil, the loss in nitrogen in the uncovered plots amounted to 34.2% in about 3 months, whereas in the covered plots the loss is only 11.6%. Similarly with 277.2 kg. of nitrogen added per acre of soil, the loss is 43.9% in the uncovered and 8.6% in the covered plot. These results conclusively prove that in presence of sunlight, ammonium sulphate is nitrified at a much greater velocity than in the dark. Along with the greater velocity of nitrification in sunlight, there is a concomitant greater loss of nitrogen in sunlight than in the dark. These results obtained in field trials strongly support our conclusion, that sunlight plays an important part in the nitrification and in denitrification in tropical countries. As the plots were not watered and as there were no showers in the months in which the experiments were carried on, the question of the passing of the nitrogen into the subsoil does not arise.

We have already emphasised that this type of denitrification, when the conditions are favourable for oxidation and nitrification of the nitrogenous compounds in the soil, is caused by the formation and decomposition of NH_4NO_2 in the process of nitrification. The formation of ammonium nitrite from ammonium salts and proteins, require oxygen, and that is why, this type of denitrification is facilitated by increased soil aeration. In the process of nitrification, the ammonium ion is replaced first, by the acidic NO_2 -ion and finally by NO_3 -ion and hence in the process of nitrification, the acidity of the system increases. It is well known that nitrous acid decomposes according to the equation

Moreover, acids have been found to facilitate the thermal and photochemical decomposition of ammonium nitrite, which is temporarily formed in the soil in the process of nitrification. Also Murty and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 985) have shown that sunlight or artificial light markedly accelerates the decomposition of nitrous acid according to the above equation. All these factors are responsible for the nitrogen loss from soils, when ammonium salts or proteins

added or present in the soil undergo nitrification. Moreover, as the soils become slightly acidic on the addition of ammonium sulphate, the loss of nitrogen from such soils cannot be due to the escape of gaseous ammonia.

In previous papers it has been emphasised that the presence of carbonaceous substances like carbohydrates, fats, etc. present in the soil along with the nitrogenous substances, retard the nitrogen loss from soils. It has been shown by us that in presence of the carbonaceous substances, the velocity of nitrification of the nitrogenous compounds is decreased and consequently the nitrogen loss is concomitantly decreased. The following field trials with the addition of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ to the soil, with or without molasses, show definitely that molasses retard the velocity of nitrification and denitrification in soils.

TABLE IIa.

1080 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 36 sq. ft., *i.e.*, 138.6 kg. of N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per acre of land used and 2.5 kg. molasses per 36 sq. ft.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Unmolassed	0.032%	0.0028%	0.0348%	0.14%	0.476%	18-1-36
Molassed	0.032	0.0028	0.0348	0.14	0.743	"
Unmolassed	0.008	0.00934	0.01734	0.1081	0.481	30-1-36
Molassed	0.0112	0.00972	0.02092	0.1179	0.745	"
Unmolassed	0.00582	0.01132	0.01714	0.1033	0.478	19-2-36
Molassed	0.010	0.010	0.02	0.1185	0.744	"
Unmolassed	0.00504	0.01194	0.01698	0.0995	0.478	9-3-36
Molassed	0.00984	0.0102	0.02	0.1172	0.744	"
Unmolassed	0.00416	0.01224	0.0164	0.0982	0.478	4-4-36
Molassed	0.00956	0.01048	0.02	0.1092	0.742	"
Unmolassed	0.00324	0.01302	0.01626	0.09212	0.478	25-7-36
Molassed	0.00896	0.01104	0.02	0.1012	0.742	

TABLE IIb.

2160 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 36 sq. ft., *i.e.*, 277.2 kg. as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per acre of land used and 2.5 kg. of molasses per 36 sq. ft. of land.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Unmolassed	0.0468%	0.0028%	0.0496%	0.2%	0.476%	18-1-36
Molassed	0.0468	0.0028	0.0496	0.2	0.743	„
Unmolassed	0.0234	0.01468	0.0380	0.167	0.481	30-1-36
Molassed	0.029	0.01504	0.044	0.1866	0.745	„
Unmolassed	0.020	0.01488	0.0348	0.1425	0.478	19-2-36
Molassed	0.0294	0.01510	0.0455	0.1788	0.744	„
Unmolassed	0.01844	0.01544	0.03388	0.1325	0.478	9-3-36
Molassed	0.02774	0.01462	0.0445	0.1725	0.744	„
Unmolassed	0.01784	0.0157	0.03354	0.1281	0.472	4-4-36
Molassed	0.0248	0.0164	0.0412	0.17	0.743	„
Unmolassed	0.00862	0.01848	0.0271	0.1122	0.472	25-4-36
Molassed	0.01856	0.02024	0.0388	0.1642	0.742	„

Thus with 138.6 kg. of nitrogen as ammonium sulphate per acre of land, the loss of nitrogen amounts to 34.2% in the absence of molasses, whilst with molasses it is 27.1%. With 277.2 kg. of nitrogen, the loss is 43.9% without molasses. With molasses the loss is only 17.9%.

It will be clear, therefore, that the value of ammonium sulphate as a manure to be used in tropical countries should be greatly enhanced, if it is mixed with molasses, fats or any other carbonaceous material. Oil-cakes containing fats and nitrogenous compounds ought to be effective in tropical countries for fats are known to retard the oxidation and nitrification of the nitrogenous compounds in the soil. It is clear, why farmyard or green manure, produces better crop yield than ammonium sulphate alone, because the carbonaceous substances present in the farmyard or green manure, retard the nitrification of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil and decrease the nitrogen loss. As a matter of fact, when farmyard manure is added to the soil more nitrogen is conserved in the soil

than with ammonium sulphate. This is evident from the following important results obtained from the Rothamsted fields:—

	Total N.
1. Receiving no manure since 1843	0.095%
2. Receiving farmyard manure since 1852	0.256
3. Receiving complete artificials $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.099
4. Receiving complete farmyard manure	0.253
5. Receiving potash and phosphate but no nitrogen	0.090

Apart from this influence of the carbonaceous substances like sugars, cellulose, fats, etc., on the conservation of soil nitrogen, these substances when added to the soil along with farmyard or green manure, or straw, also leads to the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil. Hence the carbonaceous substances, like sugars, cellulose, fats, etc. added to the soil are not only effective in nitrogen conservation, but cause nitrogen fixation as well.

It is of interest to note that after six or seven months, the plots containing ammonium sulphate alone are feebly acidic (p_n 6.9 to 6.6), whilst the plot containing ammonium sulphate and molasses show p_n 7 to 7.2.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 756) it has been shown that an aqueous solution of ammonium nitrite kept at 40° or 50° decomposes appreciably, when exposed to the total light of a gas-filled tungsten filament lamp of 1000 watt. We have investigated the decomposition of ammonium nitrite when illuminated by the same light or in the dark, when the solutions are maintained at 20° or 30°. The following are the experimental results.

TABLE IIIa.

$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ added as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.14$ g. $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ added as $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2 = 0.15$ g. Total N added = 0.29 g. in 20 c.c. of solution.

LIGHT.

Exposure at	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ left.	$\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ left.	Total N left.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ lost.	$\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ lost.	Total N lost.	% lost
30° for 5 hours	0.1343	0.1422	0.2786	0.0059	0.0058	0.0114	3.9
30° " 10 "	0.1272	0.135	0.2642	0.0128	0.013	0.0258	8.2
30° " 20 "	0.112	0.12	0.234	0.028	0.028	0.056	19.6
20° " 5 "	0.14	0.148	0.288	nil	nil	nil	nil
20° " 10 "	0.1312	0.14	0.271	0.0088	0.0088	0.019	6.5
20° " 20 "	0.123	0.132	0.257	0.017	0.016	0.033	11.3
20° " 40 "	0.1152	0.1218	0.2402	0.0248	0.0232	0.0498	17

Kept at	DARK.						
	NH ₃ -N left.	NO ₂ -N left.	Total N left.	NH ₃ -N lost.	NO ₂ -N lost.	Total N lost.	% lost
30° for 5 hours	0·14	0·148	0·288	nil	nil	nil	·1
30° „ 10 „	0·1372	0·1452	0·2855	0·0028	0·00275	0·0045	0·2
30° „ 20 „	0·1327	0·14	0·2754	0·0073	0·008	0·0146	5
20° „ 5 „	0·14	0·148	0·29	nil	nil	nil	nil
20° „ 10 „	0·14	0·148	0·29	nil	nil	nil	nil
20° „ 20 „	0·14	0·148	0·29	nil	nil	nil	nil
20° „ „	0·1318	0·14	0·2729	0·0082	0·008	0·0171	5·7

TABLE III b.

Treatment after.	Loss of nitrogen			Percentage loss in	
	Dark and light.	Dark only.	Light only.	Dark.	Light.
5 hrs. at 30°	0·01149	nil	0·01149	nil	3·9
10 hrs. at 30°	0·02589	0·0045	0·0213	0·2	8·2
20 hrs. at 30°	0·056	0·0146	0·0414	5·0	14·6
5 hrs. at 20°	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
10 hrs. at 20°	0·019	nil	0·019	nil	6·5
20 hrs. at 20°	0·033	nil	0·033	nil	11·3
40 hrs. at 20°	0·0498	0·0171	0·0327	5·7	11·5

The foregoing results show that at 39°, an aqueous solution of ammonium nitrite containing 14·5 g. of nitrogen per litre undergoes slight decomposition into nitrogen and water even in the dark. Light markedly accelerates this decomposition. At 20°, the thermal decomposition is very slight but in presence of light, the decomposition is appreciable. Hence in the soil, ammonium nitrite formed in the process of nitrification of nitrogenous compounds can decompose into gaseous nitrogen in the day time even when the soil temperature does not exceed 20°. That is why, marked nitrogen loss had been observed in heavily manured fields in Rothamsted and other experimental stations.

SUMMARY.

1. Field trials show, that nitrification of ammonium sulphate is much quicker in plots receiving sunlight, than in those covered with wooden planks. Moreover, in the uncovered plots there is more nitrogen loss than in the covered ones. Thus with 277.2 kg. of nitrogen added as ammonium sulphate per acre of land, the loss is 41.9% in the uncovered and only 8.2% in the covered plot.

2. Molasses appreciably decrease the velocity of nitrification of ammonium sulphate added to fields and also retards nitrogen loss. Thus with 277.2 kg. of nitrogen per acre of land, the loss is 43.9% with molasses and without molasses the loss is 17.9%.

3. Carbonaceous substances like sugars, cellulose, fats etc. not only conserve soil nitrogen by decreasing the velocity of nitrification and denitrification, but also cause nitrogen fixation in the soil as well.

4. An aqueous solution of ammonium nitrite containing 14.5 grams nitrogen per litre undergoes appreciable decomposition into gaseous nitrogen and water at 20° and 44° even in the dark. The total light from a tungsten filament lamp of 1000 watt accelerates the thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite. This observation explains why marked nitrogen loss has been observed in heavily manured fields at Rothamsted and other experimental stations.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY.
ALLAHABAD

Received July 31, 1936.

—